

Assessment of Challenges Affecting the Implementations of Twelve Year Basic Education Policy A Case Study of Muhanga District, Rwanda

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A RESEARCH PROJECT REPORT SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF THE MASTERS DEGREE IN EDUCATION OF THE UNIVERSITY OF KIGALI, RWANDA.

Abstract:- This research aims at assessment of challenges affecting the implementation of twelve years education policy in MUHANGA District, Rwanda specific objectives was : To evaluate challenges faced by education partners in implementing twelve years basic education policy in MUHANGA District, To elaborate the level of implementation of policy in twelve years basic education in MUHANGA District ,To examine the relationship between challenges and the implementation of Twelve years basic education in MUHANGA District. The study was conducted in 12Year Basic Education schools in Muhanga District where the whole population was 150 including teachers, head teacher, students, and parents The research used qualitative and quantitative methods. Secondary data were obtained through documentation, library and internet research. Data were collected using a questionnaire, interview guide and documentary analysis. Data were presented in tabulation formats and interpreted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Hence the following were taken major recommendations: to mobilize sufficient budget according to the needs of each school where this will help in building sustainable infrastructure and increasing other school facilities and improving the working conditions of teachers by providing adequate incentives.

Keywords: Challenges, Implementation of Twelve Years Education Policy.

I. GENERAL INTRODUCTION

➤ Introduction

This chapter introduces issues related to challenges affecting the implementation of twelve year basic education policy, at the global level, regional level and local level. Also the chapter further talks about statement of the background of the study, problem statement, research objectives, and research questions as well as the significance of the study and organization of the study.

➤ Background of the study

The government of Rwanda established a vision 2020 in order to focus on investment in education of Rwandans. As encapsulated in the vision 2020, human capital is seen as the greatest impediment to the achievement of national objectives to become a knowledge based and middle income country by

2020. Furthermore, to ensure that no child has no opportunity of basic education and the government introduced 300Frw school fees and replaced with an equivalent capitation grant (MINEDUC, 2012).The assessments will give the way for attaining EFA by 2015. The purpose of government of to increase to years of basic education from current 6 years of primary education. Given the 3 remarkable success of Twelve Year Basic Education program (MINEDUC 2014), the government has extended it to twelve Years Basic education. However, extending chance from lower to upper level in secondary schools become the rights strategic decisions used by the government of Rwanda.

The program denotes the intention to assume an increase of accessibility to large cohorts of students who should complete Twelve Years Basic Education in next period while the expectation for pooling individuals adhering the labor market. The performance in implementing Twelve years basic education is a matter to various obstacles. In fact, Twelve years basic Education policy is being implemented in all corners of the country and the researcher decided to conduct research on Twelve years basic Education policy implementation to investigate the challenges faced by the implementers of this policy As stated by Ogunshola and Adewale, (2012), education shall be directed to full development of human personality and fortifying respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. Right to education is not an end to itself, but a crucial instrument in increasing the quality of life. Education is a key to economic, development enjoyment of various human rights. Education gives a mean where all people can have awareness of their rights and duties that was very crucial elements to attain objectives of equality and peace.

➤ The specific objective of this research

- To evaluate challenges faced by education partners in implementing twelve years basic education policy in MUHANGA District.
- To elaborate the level of implementation of policy in twelve years basic education in MUHANGA District
- To examine the relationship between challenges and the implementation of Twelve years basic education in MUHANGA District

➤ *Research questions /Research hypothesis*

The research hypothesis of this dissertation was based on alternative hypothesis based on the specific objectives

H1. The challenges had a significant impact in implementing

Twelve years basic education policy in MUHANGA District

H2. There is significant impact on the implementation levels of Twelve years basic education policy in MUHANGA District

H3. There are significant impacts on the relationship between challenges and implementation level of Twelve years basic education.

II. THEORETICAL LITERATURE

This section is about the theoretical review on the subject under the study. In this sections the variables under the study are fully explained and theories related to them are detailed enough in order to increase the understanding.

➤ *Implementation of twelve years Basic Education*

As a factor conditioning means of production, education determines the kind of economy in a given society where people live (industrial or farming society). It is the education that endows people with skills competences and skills to ensure economic production. Education endows also people with skills, competences, and know- how necessary to live, and work with others.

➤ *Increased Number of School Enrolment*

Past studies evidences that the lack of school fees is among hindrances to children access to education. A study conducted in Indonesia, China, and Salomon Islands and in many of African countries demonstrated that fees are major obstacles to children's enrollment (Ehren & Honingh, 2016). A study conducted in Tanzania, parents and teachers observed that inability to pay school fees is the primary reason justifying absenteeism of children at school (Chabari, 2016). Therefore, few empirical studies on the effect of school fees to children enrolment argued that inability to enroll and the dropout rates increase or decrease. Children who did not pay additional fees were prevented to attend school. A study conducted in Uganda through econometric analysis revealed that household income to be ineffective determinant of school enrolment to the abolition of school fees (UNESCO, 2016).

➤ *Implementation of Twelve Years Basic Education in Rwanda*

According to MINEDUC (2015), the term, education" etymologically originates from the word "educere" which means taking the initiative steering, accompanying or guiding. With evolution, the term took on the different meaning. Today, "education" is defined as the use of appropriate means to achieve a complete development of a human being. In the Macmillan. (2014), the word "education" refers to the process of teaching and learning at school, college and university. Otherwise, "educating" means developing moral, physical and intellectual abilities of the human being MINEDUC (2015) assert that education affects who we are, what we know, what we believe, the way we are thinking and what we can do. It evaluates expected of persons

and country and it is the basis of all elements of the country. It is in this regards, that Rwanda established education for all with the intention to boost economic agriculture, globalization, technology, increasing the quality of life and retain political stability and democracy.

➤ *Challenges to the Implementation of Basic Education*

One of the greatest impediment to universal access to and equity in basic education in low and middle income countries is the issue of low enrolment and completion of girls (UNESCO, 2016). The international commitment to the EFA frameworks has contributed to the narrow of gender gap in education, the gap is still wide in the rural areas of sub-Saharan Africa and south west Asia. Available data from 28 countries indicate that there are still fewer than nine girls in school for every ten boys.

Attaining equity and just society necessitates a conscious effort in using discriminatory contextual policies that are favorable to girls in order to lift them from the bottom of educational ladder (Timothy, 2015). International efforts to increase access to girls in basic education have contained strategies that seek to extend incentives to parents to invest their education and increasing the availability of and thereby access to schools for girls.

➤ *Lack of enough budgets*

The elimination of schools fees and reduction of other indirect cost associated with textbooks, school uniforms and other hidden fees is the first step of making basic education affordable hence accessible to the vulnerable (UNESCO, 2015). Several studies in Africa and Latin America have revealed that fees are the biggest barrier to attain accessibility to equitable quality basic education (UNESCO, 2015). Researches in some 15 sub-Saharan Africa countries including Malawi and Uganda where fees have been abolished in one form or the other by the year 2000, have recorded sustain increase in enrolments and has narrowed that gap in access between advantaged and disadvantaged groups within a country (World Bank, 2016).

➤ *High cost of school material*

A report elucidated by the World Bank emphasized on the existence of five types of education costs in secondary schools. Most countries that charge school fees charged it unofficially. For example 2 out of 33 countries that charged tuition fee charged it unofficially and 18 of the 52 countries charging fees exploited parents. There are also other school-based activity fees that families still have to pay (World Bank, 2016).

➤ *Overpopulation in classrooms*

According to Barrow (2016), primary school as teaching and learning environment include physical, academic, social and cultural factors. Construction, equipment and infrastructures available. The cultural condition consists of rules, regulations, values and discipline. Chabari (2016) described school environment as a physical space that assists teaching and learning program such as technology, one show cost effectiveness and performance.

➤ *Working condition for teachers*

Low morale and status among teachers in primary school's phenomenon is normal. This lead to reduced productivity and poor academic performance. Teacher behaviors towards their responsibilities, students, classroom management and their interaction with students have a great impact on academic performance of them in primary schools. Jensen (2015)notes that if teachers feel they are working harder than others with similar qualification in other sectors of economy but are obtaining fewer rewards, they will fee dissatisfied with their work .

➤ *Lack of Qualified teachers*

The existing scientific evidences show the need of reform for learning, coupled with changes in curriculum focuses and deeper understanding of teacher learning and student thinking. It is argued that theories of professional development need to include both cognitive and social aspects of learning (Ogunshola & Adewale, 2012).

➤ *Research Design and Methodology*

Research designs was quantitative research plan specifying the methods and procedures for collecting and analyzing the needed information hence by knowing which research design is needed to solve the problem, help researcher to predetermine procedures that likely needed in the study. In scientific research there are three main research design; qualitative research, quantitative research and the mixed approach which can adopted for a study.

In this entire population of 150 respondents was used to gather information from key informants such as MUHANGA District Education Board. The universal sampling technique was uses to generate respondents for the interview.

Universal sampling is in which the researcher can use all data which a researcher believes to deliver the required data (Adam and Kamuzora, 2018). The advantages of universal sampling include helping the researcher in saving time and money when collecting data, it can also involve multiple phases, and it can also help the researcher to create generalizations from the data, and looking at the averages in the data, and it can also glean information from various extremes of population groups.

III. DATA COLLECTION METHODS

➤ *Questionnaire*

Structure questionnaire was used to collect data for this study. The advantage of using this method of data collection is the affordability in gathering qualitative data. It makes it quick and easy to collect and administer the data collected. The questionnaire would have five sections.

The first section would include information regarding respondents' demographic features such as age, gender and marital status. The second section would cover information regarding assessment of challenges affecting the implementation of twelve year basic education policy in MUHANGA District, Rwanda. In this section, respondents was been asked to identify the factor that makes challenges affecting the implementations of twelve year basic education

policy. The third section covered information regarding the relationship between challenges and the implementation of Twelve years basic education in MUHANGA District.

➤ *Data Analysis and processing*

It is done with the use of questionnaire and interview because it is where a researcher can reach a large group of respondents within a short time and little cost and it enables him to remain anonymous and honest in the responses given by the respondents. The data were collected for research primary data where interview, questionnaire and observations were used, research; records, documents, newspapers, magazines, journals and other documents form library were used. Brochures, trade magazines, newspapers, the internet, newspapers, relevant articles and other long essays, which cover an area the study, were used. Secondary data source is a term used in various disciplines to idea. This was been done in the following ways:

- *Editing*

This will involve cross checking questionnaires collected for any errors and unclear or contradicting responses that require clarification from the respondents. The aim would be to ensure accuracy, completeness and consistency of the data collected.

- *Coding*

This will involve categorizing of responses to determine the frequency and the resultant percentage of a particular response to facilitate drawing of conclusions on particular aspects.

- *Tables*

Frequency distribution tables was been used to summarize data collected. The tables display information obtained from the coding process in a more summarized and meaningful manner with the rationale of coming up with clear conclusions.

➤ *Validity*

Validity is the state of being effective or soundness, because something is made or done with accurate formalities or having well based argument or reasons (Adam and Kamuzora, 2018). Mays and Pope (2014) argue that there are no mechanical or easy solutions to limit the likelihood that there was been errors in qualitative research. In research, it is almost impossible to find a 100% valid instrument.

This tells why validity is usually measured in terms of degrees. Nevertheless, there are various ways of improving validity, each of which requires the exercise of judgment on the part of a researcher and a reader. In terms of measurement procedures, therefore, validity is the ability of an instrument to measure what it is designed to measure (Kumar, 2016); it is how accurately the research findings represent the phenomena they are intended to represent (Anderson, 2015); it is the credibility or of the research (UCDAVIS, 2016).

➤ *Reliability*

In qualitative research, there needs to be a way of assessing the extent to which claims are supported by convincing evidence. (Watson, 2018) Although the terms reliability and validity traditionally have been associated with quantitative research, increasingly they are being seen as key concepts in qualitative research as well. Examining the data for reliability and validity assesses both the objectivity and credibility of the research instrument.

Validity relates to the uprightness and realness of the research data instrument, while reliability relates to the reproducibility and steadiness of the data. Valuable and useful research data must be both reliable and valid. Reliability is the capability of a research instrument to generate similar results when used repeatedly under similar conditions. (Kumar, 2020).

➤ *Ethical Considerations*

In this study the researcher would consider the right of privacy of the respondents; also the researcher would consider the autonomy of the respondents, the records of the study was been considered confident. This study would strictly obey the principles of ethics in social science research. This means that respondents voluntarily participated in the study and they were not forced to give information's.

The researcher will collect information at working place and within working hours to ensure respondents 'security because of being at safe place and that no risks environment in which the study took place during the whole process of data collection and procedures of the research. Also the researcher assured the respondents confidentiality and clearly comforting them to full participation during the whole process of research. Also the researcher adhered to institution time table so that he could not interfered respondents' daily time table. The researcher followed all the procedures of data collection by asking the permission to collect data at MUHANGA District.

IV. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ *Summary of Findings*

This research was guided by three specific objectives. The first was about the challenges facing in the implementation of 12Year Basic Education, the second was about the implementation of 12Year Basic Education, and the last is about the impact of found challenges on the implementation of 12 Year Basic Education.

➤ *Challenges faced in implementing twelve year basic education policy in Muhanga District*

To the first specific objective, the challenges were divided into two categories meaning financial and non-financial challenges. Financial challenges were expressed in term of insufficient budget to renovate school infrastructures considering the mean of 3.71 wish is interpreted as high mean.

➤ *The Implementation level of twelve year basic education in Muhanga District*

To the second specific objective, it was revealed that that 12 Year basic education was effectively implemented in terms of the increase of school attendants considering the mean of 3.70 considered as high mean, access to education for poor students with the mean of 3.72 considered as high mean, decrease of educational costs considering the mean of 3.87 taken into consideration as high mean, and achievement of educational policy considering the mean of 4.04 which is interpreted as high mean.

➤ *Relationship between the financial and non-financial challenges and the implementation of 12 Year basic education in Muhanga District*

To the third specific objective established the impact financial and non-financial challenges impact implementation of 12Year Basic Education in Muhanga District through poor people have continued to have less access to education considering the mean of 3.65, stagnation of the implementation of different education policies related to 12 Year Basic Education considering the mean of 3.87 considered as high mean and lack of quality education in 12 Year Basic Education considering the mean of 3.53 and all of those well positively correlated considering the p-values of 0.000 that are less than the significance level of 0.05 with the use of one sample t-test.

V. CONCLUSION

12 Year Basic Education in Rwanda was introduced to fulfill one of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) which were turned into Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In order to meet that the government of Rwanda have vowed build an economy which is based on the education and to that the 9 Year Basic Education and 12 Year Basic Education were created in order to boost that and helping children from families with critical economic conditions. The policy of education for all has encountered with various obstacles in rural areas where they hampered the fulfillment of its objectives. In this study it has been found that financial and non-financial challenges exist and affect the quality of education.

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